

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

AI Literacy and Ethical Awareness: A Study on Educators' Preparedness for Responsible AI Use

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Abstract

Objectives: This study examined the relationship between Artificial Intelligence (AI) literacy and AI ethical awareness among educators, specifically determining their levels and testing whether a statistically significant relationship exists between the two variables. **Method:** A quantitative–correlational research design was employed. From a population of 243 educators, 151 faculty members were selected using random sampling. Data were collected using an adapted Meta AI Literacy Scale (MAILS), which demonstrated acceptable content validity and high internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.89$). Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and Pearson's correlation coefficient were used for data analysis. **Findings:** Results revealed that educators exhibited moderately low levels of AI literacy (M = 3.65, SD = 1.42) and AI ethical awareness (M = 3.70, SD = 1.39). Specifically, deficiencies were observed in higher-order competencies such as critical evaluation and practical application of AI tools. Ethical awareness was also limited, particularly in areas of bias mitigation, data privacy, and academic integrity. Correlation analysis showed a strong and statistically significant positive relationship ($r = 0.63$, $p \leq 0.05$) between AI literacy and ethical awareness, indicating that higher levels of technical competence are associated with stronger ethical understanding. These findings suggest that improving AI literacy may directly enhance educators' ethical decision-making in AI integration. **Novelty:** This study provides empirical evidence from rural Philippine State Universities and Colleges (SUCs), a context that remains underexplored in AI-in-education research. It highlights the interconnected development of AI literacy and ethical awareness and offers data-driven insights for designing capacity-building programs in resource-constrained educational settings.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; AI Literacy; AI Ethical Awareness; Education Technology; Faculty Competence

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming the educational landscape by enhancing both administrative efficiency and instructional practices. From automating routine tasks to enabling adaptive and personalized learning environments, AI technologies have significantly reshaped how teaching and learning occur⁽¹⁾. At its core, AI in education involves the application of advanced computational techniques, such as machine learning and natural language processing, to analyze large datasets, identify patterns, and support data-driven decision-making in instructional design⁽²⁾. These capabilities allow educators to tailor learning experiences to individual student needs, thereby promoting more effective and inclusive education.

Beyond its technical applications, recent international work has increasingly emphasized the need to conceptualize AI in education within structured competency frameworks. Emerging AI literacy frameworks highlight that effective engagement with AI requires not only operational skills but also critical understanding, ethical reasoning, and socio-technical awareness. Global policy initiatives such as those advocating responsible and human-centered AI integration in education, stress the importance of preparing educators to navigate both the opportunities and risks of AI technologies. These developments underscore a shift from viewing AI merely as a tool toward recognizing it as a complex system requiring informed and reflective use⁽³⁾.

Despite these promising advancements, the integration of AI in education presents several challenges. Concerns related to data privacy, algorithmic bias, system transparency, and the high cost of implementation remain critical issues⁽⁴⁾. Moreover, the emergence of generative AI technologies has further complicated the educational landscape. Unlike traditional AI systems, generative AI can produce original content—including essays, images, and multimedia outputs—raising significant questions about authenticity, authorship, and academic integrity⁽⁵⁾. While these tools offer opportunities for innovation, they also introduce risks associated with misuse and over-reliance⁽⁶⁾. These concerns are increasingly reflected in international policy discussions, which call for clearer governance structures and ethical guidelines to regulate AI use in educational settings.

Academic integrity, a foundational principle of education, is particularly vulnerable in the context of AI integration. The International Centre for Academic Integrity identifies six core values such as honesty, trust, fairness, respect, responsibility, and courage that guide ethical academic behavior⁽⁷⁾. The inappropriate use of AI-generated content, such as submitting machine-generated work as one's own, undermines these values and raises concerns about the erosion of critical thinking and independent learning. Furthermore, issues regarding the reliability and accuracy of AI-generated outputs amplify the need for careful and responsible use of such technologies⁽⁸⁾. In response, international frameworks increasingly advocate embedding ethical considerations, including transparency and accountability, into both curriculum design and teaching practice.

While debates surrounding AI in education continue, its potential benefits cannot be overlooked⁽⁹⁾. To harness these benefits effectively, educators must possess not only technical competence but also the ability to critically evaluate and ethically apply AI tools. This highlights the importance of AI literacy, which encompasses the knowledge, skills, and critical understanding required to use AI technologies responsibly in educational contexts⁽¹⁰⁾. Contemporary AI literacy frameworks further emphasize multidimensional competencies, integrating cognitive, technical, and ethical domains to ensure holistic preparedness.

Equally important is the development of ethical awareness among educators. The integration of AI necessitates careful consideration of ethical issues such as bias, data privacy, accountability, and transparency⁽¹¹⁾. Educators are increasingly required to make informed decisions regarding the appropriate use of AI, ensuring that technological advancements do not compromise educational values or equity⁽¹²⁾. International policy initiatives similarly stress that ethical competence is not supplementary but integral to effective AI use, particularly in safeguarding inclusive and equitable learning environments.

Despite the growing emphasis on AI literacy in global discourse, a critical gap remains in understanding how AI literacy relates to ethical awareness, particularly among educators in resource-constrained and rural higher education institutions⁽¹¹⁾. Existing studies predominantly focus on technical competence and are largely situated in well-resourced or Western contexts, where access to infrastructure, training, and institutional support is assumed⁽¹³⁾,⁽¹⁴⁾.

This gap is especially important to address at the present time, as the rapid proliferation of generative AI tools has intensified ethical risks, including academic dishonesty, algorithmic bias, and data privacy violations. Without sufficient empirical understanding of how educators in under-resourced settings develop both technical and ethical competencies, there is a risk that AI integration may exacerbate educational inequities rather than reduce them⁽¹⁵⁾.

In the context of rural Philippine State Universities and Colleges (SUCs), several structural and contextual challenges further complicate AI adoption. These include limited access to reliable internet connectivity, insufficient technological infrastructure, lack of formal training programs, and uneven institutional support⁽¹⁶⁾. Additionally, cultural and pedagogical factors may influence how educators perceive and engage with AI technologies. These conditions make rural SUCs a distinct and underexplored research context, where global AI frameworks may not be directly applicable without adaptation.

If this gap remains unaddressed, educators in these contexts may continue to adopt AI tools without sufficient ethical grounding, potentially leading to misuse, compromised academic integrity, and widening disparities in educational quality. Therefore, examining the relationship between AI literacy and ethical awareness in this setting is both timely and necessary⁽¹⁷⁾.

This study, therefore, investigates the relationship between AI literacy and AI ethical awareness among educators at Eastern Samar State University (ESSU). By examining whether higher levels of AI literacy correspond to stronger ethical awareness, the study contributes to ongoing international discussions by providing localized empirical evidence from a resource-constrained setting. In doing so, it offers insights into how global AI literacy and policy frameworks can be contextualized to support responsible and equitable AI integration in higher education.

1.1 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on several interrelated theories that explain how educators acquire technological understanding, develop ethical awareness, and make informed decisions when integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into educational practice. First, the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework by⁽¹⁸⁾,⁽¹⁹⁾ provides a foundation by emphasizing the importance of combining technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge to effectively integrate digital tools in teaching. Within this framework, AI literacy can be understood as part of technological knowledge, while ethical awareness supports pedagogical decision-making and responsible integration. Second, Digital Literacy Theory⁽²⁰⁾ also underpins the study by highlighting the need for individuals not only to operate digital tools but to evaluate, interpret, and engage with technology critically. Since AI literacy represents an advanced form of digital literacy, this theory suggests that technical competence contributes to more responsible and ethical use of digital technologies. Third, Rest's Ethical Decision-Making Theory (1986)⁽²¹⁾ explains how individuals recognize and respond to moral issues. AI ethical awareness aligns with this theory because educators must be sensitive to concerns such as algorithmic bias, data privacy, and academic integrity when using AI tools. Lastly, the Diffusion of Innovation Theory, supports the idea that educators' knowledge of AI influences how they adopt and use AI technologies⁽²²⁾. As individuals gain deeper understanding of AI through literacy, they are more likely to integrate it responsibly and evaluate its ethical implications. Collectively, these theories support the premise that educators with higher levels of AI literacy are better equipped to demonstrate stronger AI ethical awareness.

1.2 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study is based on the assumption that AI literacy serves as a key factor influencing AI ethical awareness among faculty members of Eastern Samar State University. AI literacy, which encompasses knowledge of AI concepts, the ability to use AI tools, and the capacity to critically assess AI outputs, is conceptualized as the independent variable. This level of understanding is expected to shape educators' awareness of the ethical dimensions associated with AI use. The dependent variable, AI ethical awareness, includes the recognition of issues such as algorithmic bias, data privacy and confidentiality, fairness, transparency, accountability, and risks related to academic dishonesty. The study proposes that educators who possess a stronger foundation in AI literacy are more capable of identifying ethical risks, making informed decisions, and applying AI tools responsibly in educational settings. Therefore, the relationship between AI literacy and AI ethical awareness is at the core of this framework, with the assumption that greater literacy results in heightened ethical understanding. The conceptual framework guides the study in assessing the respondents' AI literacy levels, evaluating their ethical awareness, determining the relationship between the two variables, and generating recommendations for strengthening ethical and responsible AI integration in education.

1.3 Objectives

In response to the increasing integration of AI in educational settings, this study aims to examine both the technical and ethical preparedness of educators. Specifically, it seeks to:

1. Assess the level of AI literacy among educators;
2. Determine the level of AI ethical awareness among educators;
3. Examine the relationship between AI literacy and AI ethical awareness; and
4. Propose evidence-based recommendations to enhance AI-related competencies and address ethical concerns in educational practice.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

The researchers used a quantitative correlational approach to look at how AI literacy connects with AI ethical awareness among educators at Eastern Samar State University's main campus. They gathered data through a survey, which made it possible to analyze the respondents' knowledge of AI and their perspectives on ethics. A quantitative–correlational design was employed because the study aims to determine the degree and direction of relationship between AI literacy and AI ethical awareness without manipulating variables. This approach is appropriate for identifying patterns and associations that can inform future interventions, particularly in emerging research areas where causal relationships are not yet established.

2.2 Respondents and Sampling

The study was conducted among educators at the Eastern Samar State University (ESSU) Main Campus, with a total population of 243 faculty members. The target respondents included full-time faculty actively engaged in teaching during the data collection period, serving as the primary inclusion criterion. A probability sampling approach was employed using simple random sampling to ensure that each member of the population had an equal chance of selection, thereby minimizing selection bias and enhancing representativeness across academic departments. The required sample size of 151 respondents was determined using Slovin's formula, which is appropriate for finite populations when a specified margin of error is applied⁽²³⁾. This sampling strategy ensured adequate representation and supported the reliability and generalizability of the study findings.

2.3 Instrumentation

The study utilized an adapted version of the Meta AI Literacy Scale (MAILS) developed by Carolus *et al.*⁽²⁴⁾ to measure AI literacy and AI ethical awareness among faculty at Eastern Samar State University (ESSU) Main Campus. The instrument was modified to better align with the educational context, particularly in capturing educators' actual engagement with AI tools and their awareness of ethical issues in instructional and academic settings.

Specifically, the original MAILS items were contextualized by rewording statements to reflect teaching-related applications of AI (e.g., use of AI in lesson planning, assessment, and research). For the AI ethical awareness component, additional emphasis was incorporated on education-specific concerns such as academic integrity (e.g., AI-assisted plagiarism), responsible AI use in student assessment, and data privacy in learning management systems. Items were also refined to explicitly address key ethical dimensions, including algorithmic bias, fairness, transparency, accountability, and informed consent, ensuring that the construct of ethical awareness is distinct yet complementary to AI literacy.

The survey instrument consisted of 23 items divided into three sections: (1) demographic profile, (2) AI literacy (15 items), and (3) AI ethical awareness (8 items). The AI literacy component assessed respondents' knowledge of AI concepts, familiarity with AI tools, and ability to critically evaluate AI-generated outputs. The AI ethical awareness component measured respondents' capacity to recognize, interpret, and make informed judgments about ethical issues arising from AI use in educational contexts.

Responses were measured using an 11-point Likert scale ranging from 0 to 10. The use of an 11-point scale, rather than more conventional 5- or 7-point scales, was intended to provide greater sensitivity and variability in responses, allowing for more nuanced discrimination of respondents' levels of literacy and ethical awareness. Prior research suggests that expanded Likert scales can enhance measurement precision, approximate interval-level data, and improve the detection of subtle differences in attitudes and perceptions, particularly in correlational studies. This level of granularity was deemed appropriate given the study's objective to examine the relationship between two closely related constructs. The scale was interpreted as follows: 0 (Very Poor), 1–3 (Low), 4–6 (Moderate), 7–9 (High), and 10 (Excellent).

Additionally, demographic variables such as age, gender, academic department, years of teaching experience, and prior exposure to AI were collected to support further analysis.

2.4 Validation of the Instrument

2.4.1. Content Validation

The instrument underwent content validation by a panel of five experts in AI, technology. The experts assessed each item for clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness in measuring AI literacy and ethical awareness. The Content Validity Index (CVI) was calculated at both the item level (I-CVI) and scale level (S-CVI) (Table 1).

Table 1. Content Validity Index

Scale	I-CVI Range	S-CVI	Interpretation
AI Literacy	0.86 – 1.00	0.88	Acceptable
AI Ethical Awareness	0.86 – 0.95	0.89	Acceptable

All items met the minimum acceptable CVI threshold of **0.80**, confirming that the instrument adequately represents the constructs of interest.

2.4.2. Pilot Testing and Reliability

A pilot study with 30 faculty members (not part of the main sample) was conducted to examine the internal consistency of the instrument. Cronbach’s alpha was used to determine reliability (Table 2).

Table 2. Internal Consistency of the instrument

Scale	Number of Items	Cronbach’s α	Reliability Interpretation
AI Literacy	15	0.87	Excellent
AI Ethical Awareness	8	0.85	Excellent
Overall Instrument	23	0.86	Excellent

All items demonstrated strong item-total correlations ($r > 0.30$), indicating that each item contributed meaningfully to the respective subscale. No items were removed or modified after the pilot, confirming the instrument’s reliability and suitability for the main study.

2.4.3. Conclusion on Validation

The content validation and pilot testing establish that the adapted MAELS instrument is both valid and reliable for assessing AI literacy and AI ethical awareness among ESSU faculty. Therefore, it was deemed appropriate for use in the main study, ensuring accuracy, consistency, and confidence in the data collected.

2.5 Data Collection Procedure

The study obtained ethical approval from ESSU and secure informed consent from participants to ensure compliance with research ethics. The survey questionnaire was given through printed copies within the ESSU main campus, adhering to best practices for survey research. Before analysis, the collected responses were screened for completeness, inconsistencies, and missing values to maintain data quality.

2.6 Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and frequency distribution, were used to summarize both demographic data and survey responses. To assess the internal consistency of the survey scales, a reliability analysis was conducted using Cronbach’s alpha⁽²⁵⁾. Furthermore, Pearson’s correlation coefficient was computed to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between AI literacy and AI ethical awareness⁽²⁶⁾.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation of Variables (n = 151)

Variable	Mean	SD	Interpretation
AI Literacy	3.65	1.42	Moderately Low
AI Ethical Awareness	3.70	1.39	Moderately Low

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics for AI literacy and AI ethical awareness among the respondents. The findings consistently indicate that both AI literacy and AI ethical awareness are at moderately low levels, suggesting that educators

possess only foundational competencies in both domains. Rather than emphasizing minor differences between mean values, the results highlight a broader pattern of limited preparedness for responsible AI integration.

3.1.1. Correlation Analysis

Table 4. Pearson Correlation between AI Literacy and AI Ethical Awareness

Variables	r	p-value	Interpretation
AI Literacy & AI Ethical Awareness	0.63	.05	Significant

A Pearson product–moment correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between AI literacy and AI ethical awareness among the respondents (Table 4). The results revealed a moderately strong, positive, and statistically significant correlation ($r = 0.63$, $p \leq 0.05$). This indicates that higher levels of AI literacy are associated with higher levels of AI ethical awareness. Conversely, respondents with lower levels of AI literacy tend to demonstrate lower levels of ethical awareness related to AI use.

The statistical significance of the correlation suggests that the observed relationship is unlikely to have occurred by chance, thereby supporting the existence of a meaningful association between the two variables. This finding underscores the interrelated nature of technical competence and ethical understanding in the context of AI integration in education.

Overall, these findings reinforce the importance of integrating both technical and ethical dimensions in professional development programs. Enhancing AI literacy may serve as a critical pathway for improving ethical awareness; however, a comprehensive approach that also addresses broader contextual and individual factors is necessary to ensure responsible AI integration in educational settings.

3.2 Observed Response Patterns

Further insights from the response patterns reveal several consistent trends. Respondents with relatively higher AI literacy scores (5–6 range) also demonstrated higher levels of AI ethical awareness, while those with lower literacy levels (1–2 range) consistently showed weaker ethical awareness. This pattern supports the positive relationship identified in the correlation analysis and aligns with prior studies indicating that technical understanding enhances the ability to recognize and evaluate ethical issues in AI use^{(22), (27)}. However, the absence of respondents in the highest scoring range (7–10) for both variables suggests a lack of advanced competence, indicating that both AI literacy and ethical awareness remain underdeveloped among the sample.

The findings indicate that educators demonstrate limited proficiency in AI literacy ($M = 3.65$, $SD = 1.42$), reflecting only basic and fragmented understanding of AI concepts. This result is consistent with existing literature, which reports that educators often possess foundational awareness but lack deeper conceptual and critical competencies required for effective AI integration^{(10), (11)}. Similarly, studies on AI readiness highlight disparities in technological competence due to differences in training, institutional support, and access to resources^{(12), (20)}. The high variability observed in this study further supports these findings, suggesting uneven exposure to AI across disciplines and contexts.

However, the results also diverge from studies conducted in more technologically advanced or well-resourced settings, where educators demonstrate higher levels of AI literacy due to stronger institutional support and structured training programs^{(3), (28)}. This contrast underscores the influence of contextual factors, particularly in rural and resource-constrained environments such as Philippine State Universities and Colleges (SUCs), where opportunities for advanced AI training may be limited.

A similar pattern is observed in AI ethical awareness ($M = 3.70$, $SD = 1.39$), which remains at a moderately low level. This finding is consistent with research indicating that educators often lack formal preparation in addressing AI-related ethical issues, resulting in reliance on intuitive rather than structured ethical reasoning^{(21), (29)}. Existing studies emphasize that ethical awareness is frequently underdeveloped due to the limited integration of AI ethics into teacher education and professional development programs^{(11), (30)}.

Nonetheless, some studies report relatively higher levels of ethical awareness among educators exposed to interdisciplinary or ethics-focused training⁽²⁷⁾, suggesting that targeted interventions can enhance ethical competence. The comparatively lower levels observed in this study highlight a gap in such initiatives within the local context.

Notably, the study found a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between AI literacy and AI ethical awareness ($r = 0.63$, $p \leq 0.05$). This finding is in agreement with emerging global evidence suggesting that technical competence and ethical understanding are interdependent^{(22), (31)}. It supports the argument that a deeper understanding of AI systems enables educators to better identify ethical risks, such as bias, privacy concerns, and misuse of AI-generated content. This is

consistent with international frameworks, including those advocated by UNESCO, which emphasize the integration of cognitive and ethical dimensions within AI literacy⁽²⁸⁾.

However, while the strength of the relationship aligns with prior studies, the overall low levels of both variables in this study suggest that the interplay between literacy and ethics may be constrained by contextual limitations. Unlike findings in more developed educational systems, where higher baseline competencies are observed, the present results indicate that both domains require simultaneous and foundational development.

In view of these findings, the study reinforces recommendations from existing literature that professional development initiatives should integrate both AI literacy and ethical awareness rather than treating them as separate competencies⁽³²⁾. Training programs should emphasize not only technical skills but also critical evaluation and ethical reasoning. Furthermore, the establishment of clear institutional policies on AI use particularly concerning academic integrity and data privacy is consistent with global calls for stronger governance frameworks⁽³⁰⁾.

The integration of AI literacy and ethics into curricula is likewise supported by prior research as a means of ensuring sustained competency development among educators and students⁽³¹⁾. Continuous assessment mechanisms are also essential to monitor progress and adapt to evolving technological demands.

Overall, the findings both align with and extend existing literature. While they confirm global trends of limited AI preparedness among educators, they also highlight the more pronounced challenges faced in resource-constrained contexts. This study contributes to the growing body of international research by providing localized evidence from a rural Philippine SUC, addressing a gap in predominantly Western-centered studies⁽²⁹⁾. By situating the findings within global frameworks while emphasizing contextual realities, the study underscores the need for inclusive and context-sensitive approaches to AI literacy development.

4 Limitations and Future Research

This study has several limitations. First, the use of a correlational design means that causation cannot be established. Second, a significant portion of the variation in ethical awareness remains unexplained, suggesting the influence of other variables not included in the study. Third, the findings are limited to a single institution, which may affect generalizability. Finally, the use of self-reported data may introduce bias.

Future research may consider using mixed-methods approaches to gain deeper insights, as well as expanding the scope to include multiple institutions. Longitudinal or experimental designs may also help establish causal relationships.

5 Conclusions

This study found that educators at Eastern Samar State University exhibit relatively low levels of AI literacy and AI ethical awareness, indicating limited preparedness for responsible AI integration. Despite this, a moderately strong and statistically significant positive relationship ($r = 0.63$, $p \leq 0.05$) was identified, suggesting that higher AI literacy is associated with greater ethical awareness.

These findings highlight the need to develop both technical and ethical competencies among educators. It is recommended that the university implement targeted training programs on AI fundamentals and responsible use, with emphasis on issues such as bias, data privacy, transparency, and academic integrity. Additionally, integrating AI literacy and ethics into the curriculum, establishing institutional guidelines, and conducting regular competency assessments are essential to support sustainable and responsible AI adoption in education.

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